

EXTREMELY DANGEROUS VICES FOR HUMAN HEALTH

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Аннотация: в этой статье мы поговорим о плохом самочувствии человека и о его алкоголизме, а также расскажем о мерах, принятых в стране, и их результатах.

Ключевые слова: курение, алкоголь, здоровье, образ жизни, потребление, событие, вред, закон.

Abstract: in this article we will talk about a person's poor health and alcoholism, as well as tell about the measures taken in the country and their results.

Keywords: smoking alcohol, health, lifestyle, consumption, event, law, harm.

Despite the fact that it has already been proven that it is extremely dangerous for human health, vices that humanity still cannot give up are drunkenness and drunkenness. In all countries of the world, strict measures are being taken to limit their consumption. As a result of this, there is a growing tendency to a healthy lifestyle and the fact that a person who wants to live a long life should refrain from playing sports, smoking and drinking alcohol is being promoted. "In our development strategy, the education of harmoniously developed young men and girls in all respects is one of our top priorities[1]". Because only by forming a harmonious generation in all respects can a healthy environment be built in our society. Therefore, given the fact that the shows and films shown through the media have a great power of influence on the consciousness of a person, it is considered a very important issue that there are no scenes of drunkenness and embroidery on the screens at all, or they are given as little space as possible. And this is a matter that will have to be approached extremely carefully. Since chestnuts have become such an integral part of everyday life, it has not been possible to completely overcome this vice, although for several years it has been fought under the leadership of the World Health Organization and many other international organizations. For example, in order to ensure the ecological purity of the planet, reduce diseases and death associated with smoking, bring the next generation to adulthood as healthy and harmonious in all respects, since 1988, may 31 is celebrated annually as the World Anti-Smoking Day. On this day, all over the world, propaganda and propaganda work is carried out aimed at showing the negative consequences of smoking, calling on humanity to abandon this vice, reducing diseases associated with chestnuts. Young people, especially minors, are again called for awareness. In addition, in 2005, at the initiative of the World Health Organization, the UN Convention on the fight against tobacco was adopted, by which time it was ratified by more than 170 countries, in which about 87% of the planet's population lives. According to the International Association of tobacco growers, tobacco is currently planted in 4 million hectares of land in 125 countries around the World[2]. This means that one percent of the arable land on the planet is allocated to tobacco cultivation. There is talk that tobacco poses a huge scale of risks to the planet, not only due to the poisonous isi at the time of smoking, but also to the harm caused by its cultivation. Studies have found that in the area where tobacco is

planted, the capacity of the land decreases so much that no other cultivated plant causes such enormous damage to the mother ground. Likewise, alcohol consumption is also considered a social problem and requires the need to carry out regular advocacy to improve the health of citizens. According to the latest data from the World Health Organization, it was noted that Uzbekistan is in third place as the most alcohol-consuming state. In the Republic, the total alcohol consumption per capita in 2010 was 3.2 liters, while in 2016 this figure decreased to 2.7 liters[3]. The harm caused by a certain level of alcohol consumption can be higher in a low-income society than in a high-income society. For example, it is argued that in developed countries, a good road infrastructure can reduce the likelihood of traffic accidents caused by alcohol consumption, while in less developed countries, on the contrary, the likelihood of alcohol-related accidents may increase. However, this does not mean that the reduction in alcohol consumption depends on the economic development of the country. In Uzbekistan, it is allowed to sell alcohol at a distance of 200 meters from the territory of kindergartens, schools, hospitals and other educational and recreational facilities. Also, since 2010, the advertising of tobacco products and alcoholic beverages has been completely suspended[4]. This was a step that caused a stir during the entire former schorör era. This was done in order to protect the growing generation from such social risks as drunkenness and chestnuts. such an approach in the country came to our national traditions, to the norms of social morality. In 2011, the law "on the distribution and restriction of consumption of alcohol and tobacco products" was adopted in 2011[5]. According to Article 18 of the law, advertising of alcohol and tobacco products is not allowed. Today, these regulatory legal acts have a positive effect on the Prohibition of advertising of alcohol and tobacco products. When it comes to promoting their consumption, the thing is much more complicated. Already, there are no means of influencing such actions, nor appropriate penalties. The law provides a definition of what is the propaganda of the consumption of alcohol and tobacco products. These are ideas, views and actions aimed at disseminating artistic images in a transparent or disguised form, which form the perception of the harmlessness of their consumption in a person who encourages the consumption of alcohol and tobacco products[6]. As can be seen, the concept has been interpreted much more widely for this reason, the identification of hidden forms of stimulation of these harmful habits is somewhat complex. This is due to the need to introduce a punitive measure for promoting the consumption of alcohol and tobacco products into the code of administrative responsibility. At the same time, on April 5, 2012, the law "on the distribution and restriction of consumption of alcohol and tobacco products" entered into force. In addition, according to the regulation "on the preparation of warning signs about the inadmissible use of alcohol and tobacco products and providing information about the place and (or) room specially allocated for the consumption of tobacco products and the procedure for their placement", approved by the order of the minister of health of November 7, 2016, signs are established that prohibit smoking in it was strictly prescribed to impose a fine in the amount of one third of the fee. According to national indicators that are being walked in our country, there has been an increase in the level of alcohol consumption. According to the data of the State Statistics Committee, the consumption of alcohol in the account of pure alcohol per capita of 15 years and older per calendar year amounted to 4.9 liters in 2020, and 5.3 liters (increased by 8%) in 2021. As a result, the incidence rate of chronic drunkenness was 18.9 per 100,000 people in 2010, while the rate was 29.9 per cent (an increase of 63% compared to 2010) by 2020. The number of people

with alcohol and alcohol-related mental illness recorded for the first time in five years was 6,899 in 2017, reaching 8,776 (1,877) by 2020[7]. From the cases mentioned, it can be seen that the current situation necessitates a radical revision of the existing legislation to combat drunkenness, as well as infrastructure, as well as a further increase in the responsibility of the competent authorities. In addition, every year in our country there are various festivals, competitions, marathons aimed at preventing smoking, protecting young people from this vice, and propaganda work is being carried out. Summing up from the foregoing, drinking, smoking is not only a plant of life, but also an equal Vice with the fact that we ourselves hit an ax on the horn on which we sit. Therefore, the faster we get rid of it, the greater the contribution we make to improving our own health and the health of those around us, ensuring the purity of nature. And for this, every smoker requires a strong will, a firm Aspiration.

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